

SOS ACTION PLAN APP

Objective of WP3 Action Plan App

Overall objective:

WP3 Action Plan App has an overall objective is to provide micro enterprise owners and managers with the knowledge and skills to identify the relevant sustainability issues to address specific to their organisation and define an action plan to approach relevant issues.

Published Results:

WP3 Action Plan APP is a state-of-the-art digital self-assessment tool that empowers users to identify priority areas for sustainable practices to be implemented through a process of self-reflection. The App generates customised action plans that guide and upskill staff to implement sustainable solutions.

What is the role of the partners?

EUEI will be responsible for:

- WP Lead / Workplan
- Design Planning
- Tool Structure, Backend and Frontend Development (Assessment Tool + Feedback Report Manager)
- Technical realisation of Questionnaire and Feedback Instructions
- Content review and integration - Pilot Testing methodology and implementation

All Partners (GIG, Momentum, ATA, NCC and EUEI):

- Ensuring linkages to WP3 and WP4

- Follow the work and research plan for the development of the framework, assessment and feedback report
- carrying out research pertaining to national and regional information
- Analysis/Feedback
- User testing
- Translation

Activities of SOS Action Plan App

3.1 WP3 Development Workshop (Online)

Virtual workshop, 6 partner reps attend and contribute, leading to:

- Shared Understanding of WP
- Sharing of knowledge and experience
- Creative collaboration in the activities development
- Clarity on approach and timelines
- Highly motivated

Date: 01/05/2024 until 30/06/2024

3.2 Development of the Sustainability Framework, Assessment Questions and Feedback Report – (Hard/paper copy)

1 x WP3 work and research plan.

1x focus group consultation with 30 Micro enterprises

1x paper copy Framework with assessment questions and answers

1x paper copy Action plan (feedback report) with pathways to upskilling and further information

Date 01/05/2024 until 31/07/2024

3.3 Programming and technical development of the online Action Plan tool

1x Online Beta version of the Action Plan hosted on the project website (EUEI)

Date 01/06/2024 until 31/10/2024

3.4 Pilot testing of the Action Plan tool

1 x User testing methodology

1x User testing survey

1x User testing report of feedback and improvements from 75 micro enterprises and 30 VET trainers and educators

Date 01/10/2024 until 30/11/2024

3.5 Implementation of improvements, optimization and publication of the tool

1x SOS Action Plan App available on Project website. Optimization will include:

- Minimising file size; quick download, less environmental impact
- Search Engine optimisation - high visibility by target users
- Embedding Accessibility tags

Date 01/12/2024 until 31/01/2025

3.6 Translation of WP3 Tool into DE, PL, ES

3 x Translated versions of the tool will be published to the SOS website and will be available to access (German, Spanish, Polish)

Date 01/12/2024 until 31/01/2025

Target Group for WP3

MICRO ENTERPRISE OWNERS

We will consult with at least 30 diverse micro-business owners during the development of the Action Plan, aiming to identify knowledge and skills gaps and relevant framework topics. As micro-enterprises are a heterogeneous group, our participants will represent various ages, backgrounds, nationalities, and industries to closely reflect the target audience. At least 75 micro-enterprises will participate in the pilot testing of the SOS Action Plan App, assessing its usefulness and relevance. Their feedback will enable partners to make necessary adjustments, ensuring the tool's effectiveness.

We will also ensure the selection of a diverse range of participants for the pilot testing. Once published in 4 languages a further 450+ micro-business owners will use the APP to generate their personalised action plan

ENTERPRISE SUPPORT AGENCIES AND NETWORKS

Through the implementation of the SOS sustainability strategy, over 200 enterprise support organisations and networks within the SOS database will gain access to the Action Plan App to introduce it to their microenterprise clients. These organisations will be spread across Europe, guaranteeing a wide geographical adoption of the resources. ATA and NCC's extensive European stakeholder contacts will ensure a broad reach and diverse engagement.